

Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

Vision, mission, objectives and core values play major role in setting up sustainable organizations. Vision and mission statements describe the organization's goals. Core values and core principles represent the organization's culture. In this paper we have discussed a model on how a higher education institution can prosper to reach its goal of 'creating innovators' through its vision, mission, objectives and core values. A model for the core values required for a prospective graduate from higher educational institutions is developed, discussed and analysed. The model identifies some of the core values which are essential for a student/graduate to become successful and stand-out in his/her life. Based on the core values, a set of core principles for higher educational institutions is developed. Finally the benefits of core values and core principles are discussed.

Keywords : Organizational Vision, Organizational mission, Organizational core values, Creating innovators.

I. Introduction

Innovators are people who developed zeal to solve any problem however complex it is by translating an idea or invention into a solution. The solution may be a good or service that creates value or for which customers will pay. Higher education institutions with innovative education models, which are properly planned and designed, having proper mission, vision, objectives, and core values, can create real innovators by increasing their student's competency. Such institutions will be sustainable for longer period and admired by their stakeholders. Thus creating innovators to serve the society should be primary goal of higher educational institutions for long time sustainability. Any higher education institution

inculcate values in its students and make them good citizen will prosper and gain appreciation as well as enhance its brand value.

Values are defined as enduring beliefs that are personally or socially preferable to converse beliefs, which transcend specific situations, and which guide selection or evaluation of behaviour (Rokeach, 1973). Schwartz (1992) and Schwartz & Bilsky (1987) identifies three 'universal human requirements' that form the basis for all values: the need for biological survival; the demand for social interaction; and social and institutional demands for group welfare. A values statement clarifies how the organization will conduct its activities to achieve the organization's mission and vision. It is a statement about how the organization will value customers, staff, other stakeholders and the community. Values statements, in general reflects common morality, frequently emphasize respect, integrity, trust, caring, excellence, etc. Innovation is one of the core values in many higher educational institutions. Innovation is an application of new idea, more effective device or process. Innovation can be viewed as the application of better solutions that meet new requirements, unarticulated needs, or existing market needs. This is accomplished through more effective products, processes, services, technologies, or ideas that are readily available to markets, governments and society. The term innovation can be defined as something original and more effective and, as a consequence, new, that "breaks into" the market or society. Evolutionary innovations (continuous or dynamic) that are brought about by many incremental advances in technology or processes and Revolutionary innovations (discontinuous innovations) are always disruptive and new. The graduates of the higher education institutions should be trained in such a way that they should do innovations in either in Business model, Enabling process, Core process, Product performance, Product system, Alternate product, Service, Networking, Distribution channel, Brand and Customer experience.

In this paper we have discussed a model on how a higher education institution can prosper to reach its goal of 'creating innovators' through its vision, mission, objectives and core values. A model for the core values required for a prospective graduate from higher educational institutions is developed, discussed and analysed. The model identifies some of the core values which are essential for a student/graduate to become successful and stand-out in his/her life. Based on the core values, a set of core principles for higher educational institutions is developed. Finally the benefits of core values and core principles are discussed. Some of the Core Values used in this model are Team Work, Respect, Responsibility, Ethics,

Etiquette, Social Service, Communication, Character & Competency, Techno-savvy & Scientific Thinking, Quest for Excellence, Courage to innovate, and Continuous improvement through life-long learning.

II. Model Vision for Higher Education Institutions

A vision presents what the organization wants to become and gives direction for the organization's future. The vision statement is the expression of institution aspiration, and is based on analysis of the institution's environment (Karen E, 2012). Vision statement contains the broad picture and the ultimate goal of the institution by keeping the objective of the institution in mind. The vision statement is an institution's clear description of what it intends *to become* within a certain timeframe. The vision statement defines the institution's strategic position in the future and the specific elements of that position with relationship to the mission statement. In some cases, the vision is that of one leader who is heading the campus (usually president/chairman). The vision statement provides an idea about the future developments of the institution. It is the overall goals of the organization.

The *model vision statement* is the institution's destination for the length of the strategic plan. It contains the specific characteristics or features that will define the organization in its future state and is used to motivate and inspire, and is understood to be achievable.

III. Model Mission for Higher Education Institutions

The mission statement delineates a clear, concise and specific description of an organization's purpose. The mission statement serves as the explanation for the existence of the organization and delineates, in precise language, why the institution exists and what operations are intended to achieve. Historically, a mission statement consists of detailed descriptions of the institution's establishment, curricular performance, culture and tradition, and current services. The mission statement also includes description of what the institution intended to do to its students. Mission statement may also include comprehensive information about everything important to know about the institution. A mission statement must be precise but at the same time it should be stated in such a way to accommodate future plans, strategies, assumptions, and expectations of the organization. An innovator should have characteristics which include, knowledge, skills, experience, intuition, analytical ability, self-motivation, zeal to achieve, commitment and confidence. He/she should be hard worker and creative thinker, identify problems and find optimum solutions using optimum amount of resources. Out of various stakeholders of a higher education institution, the two essential and

important stake holders are students and faculty. Both students and faculty have dual nature/dual positions. The students of the higher education institution are both ‘internal customer’ and the ‘output product’ of the organization. So the mission statement should contain the strategy of the organization how it will provide quality service to create internal customers as innovators and how it will mould its students as ‘innovative finished products’. Similarly a teacher has dual role as a teacher to create innovative students and as a researcher to sustain innovation. The mission statement should stress on its strategy on how it will support a faculty in the process of creating sustainable innovative students.

Thus the *model mission statement* is simply a purpose statement used to explain in one or two sentences what the institution seeks to accomplish, why it exists, and what ultimate result should be expected. Language in the mission statement is usually expressed using verbs in the infinitive (to increase, to improve, etc.) and also should identify any problems or conditions that will be changed (Karen E, 2012).

The mission and vision statements represent the current and envisioned state of the institution. The strategic plan used to develop the institution bridges the gap between the two. The mission will decide the present and the vision will decide the future of the institution.

IV. Model objectives & goals of Higher Education Institutions

Objectives and goals of an institution are general directions of the organization, its horizontal and vertical divisions to follow the mission. An objective helps set a course by giving a general direction, but an objective does not usually contain the specifics of its own completion, where as the goal connotes specific achievement; a target reached and “checked off”. The *model objectives* of the higher education institution contain :

- Objectives on education as a service
- Objectives on students overall development by considering him/her as customer
- Objectives on development of student characters by considering as a output product
- Objectives on innovations in infrastructure and teaching –learning processes
- Objectives on learner-centered paradigm
- Objectives on research & development
- Objectives on effective utilization of ICT
- Objectives on Curriculum & pedagogy
- Objectives on Partnership & collaboration

- Objectives on Faculty recruitment & development
- Objectives on student admission & training
- Objectives on social responsibility
- Objectives on sustainability, Innovations and best practices
- Objectives on leadership & commitment

V. Core Values Required for Higher Education Institutions

Values express the integrity that individuals and organizations believe in. They serve as a decision-making tool in daily interactions that guide behaviour. The core values explain what the institution stands for and the way in which it intends to conduct its activities. In some cases, these values are so important the institution has programs and assessment measures to support and sustain them as key elements. But regardless of their priority, within the context of planning and evaluation, the values statement should declare, “These are the characteristics we believe are important in *how* we do our work” (Karen E, 2012).

According to Krueger (1996), values are: “a set of beliefs that influence the way people and groups behave; they are the “soul” of the organization; effective values are deep rooted; and core values help form a social psychology that can support or overcome individual psychology.” Some of the prominent core values used in this model are Team work, Respect, Responsibility, Ethics, Etiquette, Social Service, Communication, Character & Competency, Techno-savvy & Scientific Thinking, Quest for Excellence, Courage to innovate, and Continuous improvement through life-long learning.

Core values are the deeply ingrained principles that guide an organization actions. They serve as its cultural cornerstone. An organization’s core values set the standards of conduct that are considered important and therefore guide the behaviour of individuals in the organization. The term “values” encompasses both right and wrong expectant behaviours. The various core values which are essential and to be incorporated in innovative higher education institutions under organizational core values, faculty core values, student’s core values, and other stake holders core values are listed in table 1.

Table 1 : List of core values required to create innovators in Higher Educational Institutions.

S. N.	Core values	Organizational	Faculty	Students	Other Stakeholders
1	Accountability	√	√	√	√
2	Accuracy	-	√	√	-
3	Ambition	-	√	√	-

4	Challenge	-	-	√	√
5	Character	-	√	√	-
6	Collaboration	√	√	√	√
7	Cooperation	√	√	√	√
8	Competency	-	√	√	-
9	Commitment	√	√	√	√
10	Communication	-	√	√	√
11	Community	√	√	√	√
12	Compassion	-	√	√	-
13	Control	√	√	√	√
14	Continuous improvement	√	√	√	-
15	Credibility	√	√	√	√
16	Courage	-	√	√	-
17	Dedication	-	√	√	-
18	Dependability	√	√	√	√
19	Dignity	√	√	√	√
20	Discipline	√	√	√	-
21	Diversity	√	-	-	-
22	Efficiency	√	√	√	-
23	Equality	√	√	√	√
24	Empathy	-	√	√	-
25	Empowerment	-	√	√	-
26	Enjoyment	-	-	√	-
27	Ethics	√	√	√	√
28	Etiquette	-	√	√	√
29	Fairness	-	√	√	-
30	Flexibility	√	√	√	-
31	Friendliness	-	√	√	-
32	Generosity	-	√	√	√
33	Honesty	-	√	√	-
34	Humanity	-	√	√	-
35	Inclusiveness	√	√	-	-
36	Influence	√	-	√	-
37	Innovativeness	√	√	√	-
38	Integrity	√	√	√	√
39	Learning	√	√	√	-
40	Loyalty	-	-	√	-
41	Openness	√	√	√	√
42	Optimism	-	√	√	-
43	Orientation towards customers	√	√	√	-
44	Positive zeal	-	√	√	-
45	Professionalism	√	√	√	-
45	Performance priority	√	√	√	-
46	Persistency	-	√	√	-
47	Personal development	-	√	√	√
48	Power	√	√	√	-
49	Quality	√	√	√	√

50	Quest for excellence	√	√	√	-
51	Recognition	√	√	√	√
52	Reputation	√	√	-	-
53	Research & Innovation	√	√	√	-
54	Respect to individuals	√	√	√	√
55	Responsibility & Caring	√	√	-	-
56	Safety	√	√	√	√
57	Self-respect	-	√	√	-
58	Social service	√	√	√	√
59	Smart skills	-	√	√	-
60	Stewardship	-	√	√	-
61	Student – centred model	√	-	√	-
62	Student service	√	√	√	-
63	Team work	√	√	√	√
64	Tech savvy & scientific thinking	√	√	√	√
65	Trustworthiness	√	√	√	√
66	Wisdom	-	√	√	-

(1) Organizational Core Values :

It has been established by several authors that organizational values influence organizational structure (Walsh et al. 1981, Kabanoff et al. 1995), organizational culture (Pettigrew, 1979, Schein, 1985), organizational identity (Ashforth & Mael, 1989), and organizational strategy (Bansal, 2003) thus shaping organizational goals and means to achieve those goals. Some of organizational core values are :

- Ethics : Maintaining organizational promises & purpose.
- Openness : Organizational transparency, visibility, flexibility, cooperation.
- Team Work : Collective performance of self-motivated people in the organization.
- Integrity : Organizational commitment in maintaining promises.
- Reputation : Internal and external view on organizations standards in the frame of reference of its stakeholders & publics.
- Responsibility & Caring : Organizations responsible attitude towards work and studies and consider the needs, expectations, activities and achievements of our colleagues, students, alumni and partners.
- Continuous improvement : Improvement of quality through continuous planning and sustainable efforts.
- Orientation towards customers : Finding & fulfilling customers expectations.
- Innovation : Pursuing and utilizing new creative ideas that have the potential to change the world.

- Performance priority : Setting up priorities in organizational endeavor.
- Diversity : Respecting the diversity and giving the best of composition. Establishing an employee equity program.
- Inclusiveness : Including every stakeholder in organizational planning and decision making.
- Respect to individuals : Accepting identity and integrity of individuals in the organization.
- Efficiency : Measure of organizational performance towards achieving its goal.
- Control : Maintaining actual performance in line with standard policies and procedures based on monitoring and obtaining feedback.
- Commitment : Inclination of all stake holders of organization towards achieving the goal.
- Competency : professionalism, expertise, correctness in management
- Power : Capability to reach its goal
- Cooperation : Internal cooperation among stakeholders and external cooperation with collaborators.
- Student – centred model : Students are involved in the management and development processes of the organisation, equality and equal opportunities for all students.
- Humanity : Trusting environment within personnel and between lecturers and students, consideration, helpfulness.

(2) Faculty Core Values :

The organizational core values influence the faculty core values and some of the faculty core values are :

- Team work : Collective performance of self-motivated faculty in the organization.
- Professionalism : Systematic functioning with standard policies and procedures.
- Personal development : Individual progress through proper planning.
- Commitment : Committing to great product, service, and other initiatives that impact lives within and outside the organization.
- Recognition : Identifying and encouraging faculty based on contribution.
- Collaboration : Tie up with external faculty, industry experts for curriculum development, projects and research.
- Fairness : Impartial and systematic assessment of colleagues and students.
- Excellence : Dignified authority in a given area/subject

- Honesty : Truthfulness in all works and with all people.
- Quest for Excellence : Self motivated desire to become authority in a given area/subject.
- Student service : Academic services to the students for supporting their knowledge, skills and experience enhancement.
- Research & Innovation : Discovering new things and applying them to solve problems of the society.
- Accountability : Acknowledging and assuming responsibility for actions, products
- Empowerment : Encouraging employees to take initiative and give the best. Adopting an error-embracing environment to empower employees to lead and make decisions.
- Community : Contributing to society and demonstrating corporate social responsibility.
- Innovation : Pursuing new creative ideas that have the potential to change the world.
- Integrity : Acting with honesty and honor without compromising the truth.
- Safety : Ensuring the health and safety of employees and going beyond the legal requirements to provide an accident-free workplace.
- Loyalty : Faithfulness to the institution or cause.

(3) Student Core Values :

Organizational and faculty core values influence the core values of students and some of students core values are :

- Teamwork : Collective performance of self-motivated students in the organization
- Courage to innovate : Implementing something new that adds value.
- Character & Competency : The set of capacities and moral conditions the student needs to meet the demands of reality in the society.
- Communication : The ability of a student to know and exchange information.
- Ethics : Moral principles that govern a student's behaviour or the conducting of an activity.
- Etiquette : The customary code of polite behaviour in society or among members of the class or group
- Trustworthiness : A student who is honest, who can be entrusted with secrets or with anything else of importance.
- Responsibility/Accountability : The ability or state or fact of having a duty to deal with his studies or of having control over his studies.

- Integrity : A student having the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles.
- Innovativeness : The skill and imagination to create new things or new solution to a problem.
- Self-motivation : Initiative to undertake or continue a task or activity without another's prodding or supervision.
- Safety awareness : Conscious knowledge of one's own character, feelings, motives, and desires.
- Continuous improvement : : Improvement of student quality through continuous planning and sustainable efforts.
- Openness : Individual transparency, visibility, flexibility, cooperation.
- Service to others : Some help to the society which cannot be bought or measured with money.
- Self & mutual Respect : Considering others like me who have a positive self-esteem.
- Community involvement :
- Quality : The standard of something as measured against other things of a similar kind;
- Smart skills : Skills required to become leader and innovator.
- Quest for Excellence : Self motivated desire to become authority in a given area/subject.
- Techno-savvy & Scientific Thinking : Simplifying the day today problems using technology and applying scientific thoughts while problem solving.
- Dedication : Dedication signifies purposeful orientation and loyalty.

(4) Other stakeholders Core values :

Other stakeholders like parents, industry executives, staff members and publics living in the neighbourhood are influenced by organizational, faculty, and students core values. Some of the other stakeholders expected core values are :

- Regular monitoring & follow-up : Parents are responsible for their wards development by regular monitoring and follow-up.
- Encouragement : The process of motivation to support to realize the goal.
- Project Internship : Opportunity given by industries to the students for getting working knowledge.

- Field work opportunity : Opportunity given by NGO's to the students for getting field experience.
- Scholarships : Financial encouragement given by some organizations to support bright students.
- Suggestions for improvement : Parents and other stakeholders feedback for improvement of education quality.
- Guidance and mentoring : Opportunities, training and support by industry experts.

Figure 1 shows a model on interdependency of different types of core values of a higher education institution. The model shows the influence of organizational core values developed by organization administrators on faculty core values and the influence of faculty core values on student core values and students core values on other stakeholders core values in the process of "Creating Innovators".

Fig. 1 : Model on core values of higher educational institution to create innovators

VI. Core Principles

A set of core principles are developed based on the model of core values. These principles derived from core values as best practices required in higher education institutions to become successful in the process of realizing their goal.

Core Principle I: Industry-Collaborated

Extensive connectedness with industry is the hallmark of higher educational institutions. Both undergraduate and post graduate programmes should be planned with extensive internship and industry based research projects ensuring rich hands-on experience at the workplace. Industry professionals should be the part of curriculum design and teaching as visiting faculty to maximize the relevance.

Core Principle II: Student-Centric

In the traditional teaching – learning process of college teaching, most class time is spent with the professor lecturing and the students watching and listening. The students work individually on assignments, and cooperation is discouraged. *Student-centered teaching methods* shift the focus of activity from the teacher to the learners. These methods include active learning, in which students solve problems, answer questions, formulate questions of their own, discuss, explain, debate, or brainstorm during class; cooperative learning, in which students work in teams on problems and projects under conditions that assure both positive interdependence and individual accountability; and inductive teaching and learning, in which students are first presented with problems and learn the course material in the context of addressing the problem. Student-centered methods have repeatedly been shown to be superior to the traditional teacher-centered approach to instruction.

Core Principle III : High Quality Faculty

The higher education institutions should realize that the need of the hour is to create a conducive environment and provide incentives to attract and retain high quality faculty so that the students and the organization will get best. The faculty members having research degrees, publishing high quality research work, winners of teaching and research awards consistently, and having international reputation should be encouraged.

Core Principle IV : Professional Oriented & Technology-Supported

Higher education should be designed and delivered professionally using cutting-edge technology in all activities to improve transparency, convenience and to sharpen student's professional skills. Professional experience can be provided through adding online components and video based lectures to add professional touch to classroom based active learning through information communication technology. Technology has not only been instrumental in addressing the demand-supply gap for quality education, but has fundamentally changed the nature of several educational processes.

Core Principle V: Innovation & Excellence

Higher educational institutions should develop legacy in innovation in teaching – learning process. They should embrace this legacy by seeking transformational events to make a step change in quality and recognition and nurtures new ideas. New ideas must be protected from the dominance of *status quo*. The higher education institutions must become an experimental studio to test new ideas, free from constraints imposed by rigid organizational structures and encourage innovation that leads to excellence.

Core Principle VI: Research-Driven

Being nurtured in a research culture, students of higher education institutions are equipped with a mindset for solving problems across all walks of life. Recruiters look forward to seek such talent as their research expertise makes them more competent workers. Individuals are rewarded by great career opportunities that a research mindset enables. Recognizing the importance of research, higher education institutions have to design their programmes to enrich students with a research culture through specific courses, R & D projects and the inspirational Lecture Series by eminent persons from academia and industry,

Core Principle VII: Seamless

Seamlessness is an all-pervasive concept that manifests across higher education programme structure, curriculum, academic operations, regulations, teaching-learning strategies, modes of education delivery and external linkages. Doing full justice to the concept requires extensive changes to the prevailing practices in higher education. While recognizing the merit of such changes, higher education institutions should be committed to function within the existing regulatory framework and will institutionalize Seamlessness in a phased fashion over time. The initial courses begin with several key dimensions of Seamlessness to enhance student experience. Each student must construct a significant portion of his/her own curriculum with the guidance of faculty members. Seamlessness means providing students with the occupational, spatial and temporal mobility demanded by today's globalized economy. Seamlessness is about maximizing students' choices and ensuring that they receive all-round holistic education with no constraints.

Core Principle VIII: Continuous Improvement

To achieve excellence in everything the students of higher education institutions should be trained and educated for continuous improvement lifelong so that they will be obsolete in knowledge, skills & experience.

Core Principle IX: Creating Innovators & Employable Graduates

Higher Education institutions should develop a teaching-learning model which creates innovators and also have responsibility of making education-industry relevant and practical would be the right way to ensure a highly employable talent pool.

VII. Benefits of Core Values and Core Principles

The various benefits due to well planned organizations core values and their performance to create innovators and lifelong learners are :

- **Encourage Students:** The primary mission of higher education institutions is not only to educate students in their chosen disciplines, but also to encourage and inspire them to become innovators, leaders, and positive contributors to society.
- **Support Faculty and Staff:** The faculty inspire and direct the students academically, from basic education to discovery and the creation of new concepts, systems, and products. The staff delivers effective administrative services and partner with the faculty to ensure an excellent student service.
- **Promote Diversity and Excellence:** To remain both relevant and attract the highest calibre of students, faculty, and staff, higher educational institutions must ensure that the community is inclusive and open to all viewpoints. A culture of excellence must pervade the institution in both academic and non-academic areas.
- **Develop Leadership and Ethical Decision-Making:** Leadership and ethical decision-making are essential for growth of the person and the organization. Leadership development is an important component of education for all segments of the faculty, students, and staff. Succession planning is required to continuously promote excellence.
- **Increase Reputation:** The higher educational institution will get benefit from the international recognition so that the institution has to strive for such recognition. Pre-eminence in several academic areas must be achieved to gain the international reputation.
- **Optimize Resource Management:** The financial well-being of the institution is critical for success. By embracing responsibility-centered management to achieve financial strength and expect that all the stake holders, including alumni, are responsible for enhancing the resources.
- **Utilize Alumni:** The greatest legacy higher education institutions are alumni and their many contributions to business and society. By utilizing alumni in planning for the future of the institution and rely upon them for their involvement and philanthropic support for institutional development.

VIII. Conclusion

A model for the core values required for a prospective graduate from higher educational institutions is developed, discussed and analysed. The model identifies some of the core values which are essential for a student/graduate to become successful and stand-out in his/her life. Based on the core values, a set of core principles are developed. These principles

derived from core values as best practices required in higher education institutions to become successful in the process of realizing their goal. Finally the benefits of core values and core principles are discussed. The prominent core values used in this model for students are Team work, self & mutual respect, responsibility, ethics, etiquette, social service, communication, character & competency, techno-savvy & scientific thinking, quest for excellence, courage to innovate, and continuous improvement through life-long learning.

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